

РОЗРОБКА СИСТЕМИ ПРОСТОРОВОЇ ОРІЄНТАЦІЇ З ГАПТИЧНИМ ЗВОРОТНИМ ЗВ'ЯЗКОМ ДЛЯ ОСІБ З ПОРУШЕННЯМИ ЗОРУ

Повшенко О.А.,

Національний технічний університет України «Київський політехнічний інститут імені Ігоря Сікорського», Д.ф., асистент

Антонюк В.М.

Національний технічний університет України «Київський політехнічний інститут імені Ігоря Сікорського», студент кафедри АСНК

DEVELOPMENT OF A SPATIAL ORIENTATION SYSTEM WITH HAPTIC FEEDBACK FOR PEOPLE WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS

Povshenko O.,

National Technical University of Ukraine

“Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute”, PhD, assistant lecturer

Antoniuk V.

National Technical University of Ukraine

“Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute”, student

АННОТАЦІЯ

У статті розглянуто розробку автоматизованої системи просторової орієнтації з гаптичним зворотним зв'язком для осіб з порушеннями зору, призначеної для підвищення безпеки та автономності пересування у міському середовищі. Запропоновано апаратно-програмний комплекс у формфакторі натільного пристрою на базі мікроконтролера, матричних Time-of-Flight сенсорів та модулів тактильного оповіщення. Описано структурну та принципову схеми системи, алгоритм обробки сенсорних даних у реальному часі та метод перетворення відстані до перешкод у гаптичну індикацію. Розглянуто реалізацію динамічної адресації I2C-пристроїв, принципи ШІМ-керування вібраторами, а також особливості проектування друкованої плати й ергономічного 3D-корпусу. Практична цінність роботи полягає у створенні енергоєфективної та масштабованої системи, здатної підвищити мобільність, безпеку та самостійність користувачів.

ABSTRACT

The article presents the development of an automated spatial orientation system with haptic feedback for people with visual impairments, aimed at improving safety and autonomous mobility in urban environments. A hardware-software complex in the form of a wearable device based on a microcontroller, matrix Time-of-Flight sensors, and tactile notification modules is proposed. The structural and circuit diagrams of the system, the real-time sensor data processing algorithm, and the method of converting the distance to obstacles into haptic indications are described. The implementation of dynamic I2C device addressing, PWM control of vibration motors, as well as the design features of the printed circuit board and ergonomic 3D enclosure are considered. The practical significance of the work lies in the creation of an energy-efficient and scalable system capable of improving users' mobility, safety, and independence.

Ключові слова: вбудовані системи, просторова орієнтація, мікроконтролер, автоматизовані системи, дальномір, гаптичний зворотній зв'язок.

Keywords: embedded systems, spatial orientation, microcontroller, automated systems, distance sensor, haptic feedback, Time-of-Flight.

Introduction. Modern solutions designed to assist visually impaired people in spatial orientation are primarily based on two main approaches: the use of audio signals and tactile navigation aids such as white canes and similar assistive devices. The traditional white cane remains one of the most common and accessible orientation tools. It allows users to detect physical obstacles, road irregularities, curbs, and other objects directly along the walking path [1]. However, this method has

several obvious limitations. A cane cannot predict obstacles at a distance, does not provide information about hazards located above waist level, and requires continuous physical interaction with the surrounding environment.

To improve user safety and comfort, electronic “smart” canes (Fig.1) equipped with ultrasonic sensors, GPS navigation, and smartphone connectivity have been developed [2].

Figure 1. Most Common Assistive Devices for Spatial Orientation

Recent studies demonstrate significant progress in the development of assistive navigation systems for visually impaired people. Modern wearable travel aids increasingly combine ultrasonic sensors, LiDAR technologies, RGB-D cameras, computer vision algorithms, and GPS navigation modules to improve obstacle detection accuracy and environmental awareness [3]. In particular, smart canes based on 2D LiDAR and RGB-D sensors are capable of recognizing obstacles, estimating distances, and supporting navigation in dynamic environments [3]. Other wearable assistive systems utilize combinations of ultrasonic sensors and computer vision methods for real-time obstacle recognition and classification, increasing the reliability of navigation in complex urban conditions [4]. Furthermore, current research emphasizes the importance of ergonomic design, energy efficiency, intuitive feedback mechanisms, and seamless integration into daily life [5]. Despite these advancements, many existing systems still rely heavily on audio feedback, have limited spatial coverage, or remain expensive and difficult to use, which highlights the relevance of developing compact and energy-efficient haptic-based spatial orientation systems for visually impaired users [3-5].

These devices are capable of warning users about obstacles at a distance, usually through audio or vibration signals. Nevertheless, such approaches may introduce additional difficulties during practical operation.

Audio-based systems implemented in mobile applications, GPS navigators, and specialized smart glasses also provide information about movement direction, object location, or proximity to a target destination. However, excessive dependence on sound signals overloads the auditory channel, which is the primary means of environmental perception for visually impaired individuals. In urban environments, this issue becomes particularly critical because background noise

generated by vehicles and surrounding people significantly reduces the effectiveness of audio navigation systems. Furthermore, the use of headphones or continuous voice prompts may prevent users from hearing important real-world warning sounds, such as approaching traffic or emergency signals. In addition, many modern assistive devices remain expensive, require frequent battery charging, and are often difficult to use for elderly people.

Despite significant progress in the development of modern assistive navigation technologies [6-10], several important problems still remain unresolved. First, most existing solutions rely heavily on auditory feedback, which leads to sensory overload of the hearing channel. Since hearing serves as the primary sense for environmental interaction in blind and visually impaired people, excessive audio information may not only reduce orientation efficiency but also create dangerous situations when critical environmental sounds are missed. Second, many existing devices are capable of detecting only specific types of obstacles or operate within a limited scanning sector, which prevents users from obtaining a complete spatial representation of the surrounding environment [11]. Third, the complexity of operation, limited battery life, and high manufacturing costs reduce the accessibility of such systems for a significant number of potential users. Finally, the lack of seamless integration into everyday life results in many visually impaired individuals continuing to rely exclusively on traditional white canes for navigation [12].

Problem Statement. The rapid development of embedded systems and intelligent assistive technologies has created new opportunities for improving the mobility and safety of people with visual impairments. Despite the existence of traditional navigation aids, such as white canes and guide dogs, these solutions have several limitations related to obstacle detection range, environmental awareness, and user adaptability.

Therefore, the development of wearable automated spatial orientation systems capable of real-time obstacle detection and intuitive feedback generation is an important scientific and technical problem.

The proposed spatial orientation system is designed as a wearable device intended for everyday use in both indoor and outdoor environments. The operating conditions of such a system impose strict requirements on its ergonomic characteristics, energy efficiency, reliability, and resistance to external disturbances. The main purpose of the system is to increase the autonomy and safety of visually impaired users by detecting surrounding obstacles and transmitting information through haptic feedback.

The functionality of the proposed automated spatial orientation system is represented in the use case diagram shown in Fig. 2. The primary actor of the system

is a visually impaired user interacting with the wearable navigation device during everyday mobility scenarios. The operation process begins with system activation, after which the device automatically performs a self-diagnostics procedure to verify the correct operation of the sensors, communication interfaces, and haptic feedback modules.

After successful initialization, the system continuously performs spatial scanning of the surrounding environment using integrated distance sensors. Environmental obstacles detected during scanning are analyzed in real time by the embedded control unit. Depending on the measured distance to nearby objects, the system generates different levels of haptic notifications. When an obstacle is located within a moderate distance range, the user receives obstacle proximity indications through vibration feedback.

Figure 2. Use Case Diagram of the Spatial Orientation System

If the detected object approaches a critical distance threshold, the system activates intensified critical proximity warnings to increase user awareness and safety.

The use case diagram also illustrates the interaction between the automated system and external entities, including the surrounding environment and the power source. The environment acts as the source of obstacles and spatial information processed by the sensing subsystem, while the power source supports battery charging and autonomous operation of the wearable device. Through these interconnected functional scenarios, the system provides continuous spatial awareness and intuitive non-audio navigation assistance for visually impaired users.

The system must operate effectively under different environmental conditions. Indoor navigation scenarios are characterized by a high density of static and dynamic obstacles at short distances, requiring low-latency sensor processing and rapid generation of haptic responses. Outdoor operation introduces additional challenges caused by direct sunlight interference affecting infrared ToF sensors. Consequently, the software architecture must include filtering algorithms capable

of suppressing optical noise and maintaining stable obstacle detection accuracy.

Another important challenge concerns the physiological characteristics of visually impaired users. Since hearing often serves as the primary channel of environmental perception, the system must minimize acoustic noise generated by vibration motors and mechanical resonance of the enclosure. Furthermore, continuous monotonic vibration may lead to tactile adaptation, reducing the effectiveness of haptic perception. To address this issue, the system should generate pulsed vibration patterns with dynamically adjustable pause intervals depending on the spatial situation.

Based on these operating conditions, the following development objectives are formulated:

- development of the general structural architecture of the spatial orientation system;
- selection of a modern microelectronic component base;
- design of the electrical schematic and printed circuit board topology;
- implementation of real-time sensor data acquisition and processing algorithms;

- development of a dynamic I2C addressing mechanism for identical ToF sensors;
- implementation of PWM-based vibration motor control algorithms;
- creation of an ergonomic wearable enclosure suitable for daily use;
- verification of system reliability, energy efficiency, and tactile feedback recognition.

The proposed system should provide continuous spatial scanning in three independent sectors, ensure obstacle detection with minimal response delay, support autonomous operation for several hours, and maintain stable functionality under varying environmental conditions. The practical significance of the work lies in the development of a scalable, maintainable, and energy-efficient assistive navigation system capable of improving mobility, safety, and independence for visually impaired users.

The aim of this work is to develop and investigate an automated wearable spatial orientation system with

haptic feedback for visually impaired people, capable of detecting surrounding obstacles in real time and providing intuitive non-audio navigation assistance. The study focuses on the design of the hardware and software architecture of the system based on embedded microcontroller technologies, Time-of-Flight distance sensors, and vibration feedback modules. Particular attention is devoted to the implementation of real-time spatial scanning algorithms, haptic warning generation, energy-efficient operation, and ergonomic integration of the device into a wearable form factor suitable for everyday use in both indoor and outdoor environments.

Development of the General System Architecture. The structural diagram shown in Fig.3 represents the overall hardware architecture of the proposed spatial orientation system intended for visually impaired users [13]. The system is designed according to a modular approach and consists of a central control unit, a power supply subsystem, and three independent sensing and haptic feedback channels assigned to different spatial sectors.

Figure 3. Use Case Diagram of the Spatial Orientation System

The core element of the architecture is a microcontroller responsible for sensor polling, real-time data processing, and generation of control signals for the haptic feedback modules. Environmental scanning is performed using three optical distance sensors connected to the controller through a shared I2C communication bus. The monitored space is divided into three sectors: left, central, and right, which enables directional obstacle detection and improves spatial awareness.

The sensing subsystem is implemented using three independent distance sensors that provide continuous spatial scanning of the surrounding environment. According to the structural diagram, the total field of view of the system is divided into three angular sectors. The left sector covers the range from -135° to -45° , the central sector monitors the frontal area within -45° to 45° , while the right sector scans the space in the range from 45° to 135° . All optical sensors are connected to the microcontroller in parallel through a common I2C

digital communication bus. Such a topology supports the implementation of a dynamic software-based addressing algorithm, allowing identical sensor modules to operate on the shared bus without address conflicts.

Each sensing channel includes a distance sensor, a motor driver, and a vibration motor. After processing the measured distance values, the microcontroller generates PWM control signals that regulate the vibration intensity depending on obstacle proximity. The motor drivers operate as power switching stages and provide sufficient current for the vibration motors while electrically isolating the sensitive digital circuitry from power disturbances caused by inductive loads.

The power supply unit delivers electrical energy to all system components and separates the logic and power circuits to improve system stability and electromagnetic compatibility. Such an architecture ensures reliable operation, scalability, and intuitive haptic representation of surrounding obstacles in real time.

Selection of Electronic Components and Development of the Electrical Schematic. To implement the proposed spatial orientation system, a preliminary selection of the required electronic components was carried out considering the functional, energy, and ergonomic requirements of the wearable device. Particular attention was devoted to the compatibility of the sensing, control, and haptic feedback subsystems, as well as to the reliability of real-time operation under varying environmental conditions.

The development of the electrical schematic of the peripheral board was based on the integration of two key functional subsystems: the spatial scanning module and the haptic feedback module. The sensing subsystem was implemented using a high-precision matrix Time-of-Flight (ToF) distance sensor [14,15] responsible for obstacle detection and distance measurement. The haptic feedback subsystem consists of a DC vibration motor [16] controlled through a dedicated motor driver implemented as a semiconductor bridge stage. Integrating the optical sensing and electromechanical actuation components on a common printed circuit board significantly improves the compactness and modularity of the final wearable device.

To ensure stable operation of the active components, the schematic includes a set of passive electronic elements used for power filtering, signal stabilization, and noise suppression. Special attention was paid to local decoupling of the power supply lines because the vibration motors generate impulse electromagnetic interference during operation. For this purpose, filtering and bypass capacitors were added near the motor driver and directly across the motor terminals to suppress high-frequency noise and voltage spikes. Similar filtering measures were implemented for the sensitive digital circuitry of the ToF sensor.

The communication subsystem is based on the I2C digital interface, which enables parallel connection of multiple peripheral modules to the central microcontroller. Pull-up resistors and stabilization components were included in the schematic to guarantee reliable data transmission and stable logical states on the communication and control lines. In addition, the modular architecture of the system required the implementation of duplicated connectors for power distribution and I2C signal routing, enabling chain-type connection of multiple peripheral modules while reducing the total number of interconnecting wires inside the device enclosure.

The central control unit of the system was implemented using the STM32F411CEU6 32-bit microcontroller [17], selected due to its computational performance, low power consumption, and support for real-time peripheral communication. The main control board also includes a battery charging subsystem based on a USB Type-C interface, a Li-Pol battery management circuit, a DC-DC voltage stabilization stage, and dedicated connectors for peripheral sensor-actuator modules. Such an architecture provides stable power distribution, scalable modular integration, and reliable operation of the spatial orientation system.

Circuit Connection Description. The peripheral board connection scheme is based on a modular sensor-actuator architecture. Each peripheral module includes a Time-of-Flight distance sensor, a motor driver, and a vibration motor. The ToF sensor is connected to the main microcontroller through the I2C interface using the SDA and SCL lines, while the power supply is provided from the stabilized 3.3 V bus. To ensure reliable data transmission, the I2C bus uses pull-up resistors placed on the main control board, which prevents excessive parallel resistance when several identical modules are connected simultaneously.

The vibration motor is not connected directly to the microcontroller because its current consumption exceeds the allowable output current of the microcontroller pins. Therefore, a dedicated motor driver is used as an intermediate power stage. The microcontroller generates a PWM control signal, which is applied to the driver input. The driver switches the motor supply current and regulates the vibration intensity according to the duty cycle of the PWM signal. This solution protects the microcontroller from overloads and enables smooth control of the haptic feedback level.

For stable operation, the circuit also includes filtering capacitors placed near the sensor, motor driver, and motor terminals. These elements suppress voltage fluctuations and high-frequency interference caused by motor switching. The duplicated connectors on the board allow several modules to be connected in a chain, transmitting common power and I2C signals while keeping individual control lines for each haptic channel. This connection scheme reduces the number of wires inside the wearable device and simplifies final assembly.

The battery charging subsystem based on the TP4056 [18] (Fig.4) lithium battery charging controller and the USB Type-C interface connector USB4515-GF-A was used.

Figure 4. Connection Diagram of the TP4056 Battery Charging Controller and USB Type-C Interface

The circuit provides safe charging of the Li-Pol battery, power input stabilization, and status monitoring of the charging process. Pull-down resistors connected to the CC1 and CC2 lines ensure correct operation of the USB Type-C interface in power delivery mode. The TP4056 controller performs constant-current/constant-voltage charging and generates the FULL_BATT status signal used by the microcontroller to monitor battery charging completion.

Algorithm of System Operation. The operation algorithm of the proposed spatial orientation system is based on continuous real-time execution of several interconnected processes responsible for obstacle detection, sensor data processing, and haptic feedback generation. After powering on, the microcontroller initializes the peripheral modules and performs dynamic addressing of the connected Time-of-Flight sensors to avoid conflicts on the shared I2C communication bus.

During operation, the system cyclically polls the distance sensors assigned to different spatial sectors and processes the acquired distance values. The measured data are converted into PWM control signals that regulate the intensity of the vibration motors depending on obstacle proximity. The closer the obstacle, the stronger the generated haptic feedback.

To ensure stable real-time operation and reduce power consumption, the algorithm incorporates energy

management mechanisms, including periodic sleep modes for the microcontroller and peripheral modules between measurement cycles. The modular software architecture simplifies system scalability, debugging, and future expansion of additional sensing zones or feedback channels.

Experimental Evaluation and Discussion of Results. Experimental evaluation of the developed spatial orientation system was conducted to assess obstacle detection performance, system response time, and the effectiveness of haptic feedback generation under different operating conditions. Testing was performed using obstacles positioned at various distances within the operating range of the Time-of-Flight sensors in both indoor and outdoor environments.

During the experiments, the system demonstrated stable operation of the sensing subsystem and reliable communication through the shared I2C bus. The implemented dynamic addressing mechanism successfully prevented conflicts between identical ToF sensors connected in parallel. Particular attention was devoted to evaluating the delay between obstacle detection and vibration activation, since this parameter directly affects the quality of spatial perception and user safety. The obtained experimental results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Experimental Response Time of the Spatial Orientation System	
Distance to obstacle, m	Average response time, ms
0.2	28
0.5	31
1.0	34
1.5	38
2.0	42

The graphical representation of the obtained measurements is shown in Fig. 5.

Response time of the spatial orientation system

Dependence of the average system response delay on obstacle distance during experimental evaluation.

Figure 5. Dependence of System Response Time on Obstacle Distance

Analysis of the obtained results confirms that the proposed system satisfies the real-time operation requirements. The average response delay remained below 50 ms for all investigated distances, ensuring timely generation of haptic feedback and stable user orientation in space. The increase in response time at larger distances is associated with additional processing and filtering of sensor data; however, the obtained values remain acceptable for wearable assistive applications.

The experimental evaluation also demonstrated the effectiveness of the implemented haptic feedback approach. Users were able to intuitively distinguish both the direction and approximate proximity of obstacles according to vibration intensity and activation sector. Furthermore, the modular architecture showed stable operation during prolonged battery-powered testing and allowed reliable simultaneous operation of all sensing channels.

Conclusions. This work presented the development of an automated wearable spatial orientation system with haptic feedback intended for visually impaired users. The proposed system combines embedded microcontroller technologies, Time-of-Flight distance sensors, and vibration-based tactile feedback to provide real-time obstacle detection and intuitive non-audio spatial awareness.

During the research, the general system architecture, electrical schematics of the main and peripheral boards, and the software control algorithm were developed. The implemented modular architecture enabled independent operation of three spatial scanning sectors and ensured reliable communication between peripheral modules using the shared I2C bus with dynamic sensor addressing. The designed haptic feedback sub-

system successfully converted measured obstacle distances into vibration signals with varying intensity depending on obstacle proximity.

Experimental evaluation confirmed stable real-time operation of the developed system. The measured response delay varied from 28 ms at a distance of 0.2 m to 42 ms at a distance of 2.0 m, remaining below the required real-time threshold of 50 ms for all investigated operating conditions. These results confirm the ability of the system to provide timely obstacle indication and stable user orientation in dynamic environments.

The conducted experiments also demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed haptic interaction approach, allowing users to distinguish both the direction and approximate proximity of obstacles according to vibration intensity and activation sector. Furthermore, the developed hardware architecture demonstrated good scalability, energy efficiency, and suitability for wearable implementation. The use of power management mechanisms and modular peripheral design improved system stability and reduced overall power consumption during continuous operation.

The practical significance of the work lies in the creation of a compact, repairable, and energy-efficient assistive navigation device capable of improving mobility, safety, and independence for visually impaired people in everyday environments. Future research may focus on integrating computer vision methods, adaptive filtering algorithms, and intelligent obstacle classification techniques to further increase system functionality and navigation accuracy.

References

1. Aziz M. Z., Singh A. Obstacle Detection and Warning Systems for Visually Impaired: Survey on

Sensor Technologies and Feedback Methods // Journal of Sensors. – 2017. – Vol. 2017. – P. 1–19.

2. Nair N., Hassan S., Sulaiman S. Smart Walking Stick for Visually Impaired People with Obstacle Detection and Navigation Capabilities // Procedia Computer Science. – 2020. – Vol. 165. – P. 292–299.

3. Mai C., Chen H., Zeng L., Li Z., Liu G., Qiao Z., Qu Y., Li L., Li L. A Smart Cane Based on 2D LiDAR and RGB-D Camera Sensor—Realizing Navigation and Obstacle Recognition // Sensors. – 2024. – Vol. 24, No. 3. – Art. 870. – DOI: 10.3390/s24030870.

4. Mocanu B., Tapu R., Zaharia T. When Ultrasonic Sensors and Computer Vision Join Forces for Efficient Obstacle Detection and Recognition // Sensors. – 2016. – Vol. 16, No. 11. – Art. 1807. – DOI: 10.3390/s16111807.

5. Hersh M. Wearable Travel Aids for Blind and Partially Sighted People: A Review with a Focus on Design Issues // Sensors. – 2022. – Vol. 22, No. 14. – Art. 5454. – DOI: 10.3390/s22145454.

6. Martins M. M., Santos C. P., Frizzera A., Ceres R. Assistive Mobility Devices Focusing on Smart Walkers: Classification and Review // Robotics and Autonomous Systems. – 2012. – Vol. 60, No. 4. – P. 548–562.

7. Flor-Unda O., Arcos-Reina R., Toapanta C., Villao F., Bustos-Estrella A., Suntaxi C., Palacios-Cabrera H. Challenges in the Development of Exoskeletons for People with Disabilities // Technologies. – 2025. – Vol. 13, No. 7. – Art. 291.

8. Lakde C. K., Prasad P. S. Navigation System for Visually Impaired People // Proceedings of the 2015 International Conference on Computation of Power, Energy, Information and Communication (ICCPEIC). – 2015. – P. 93–98. – DOI: 10.1109/ICCPEIC.2015.7259483.

9. Chen D., Zhang Y., Hu X., Chen G., Fang Y., Chen X., Song A. Development and Evaluation of Refreshable Braille Display and Active Touch-Reading System for Digital Reading of the Visually Impaired // IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering. – 2024. – Vol. 32. – P. 934–945.

10. Rosa J. R. D. S., Valentim N. M. C. Accessibility, Usability and User Experience Design for Visually Impaired People: A Systematic Mapping Study //

Proceedings of the 19th Brazilian Symposium on Human Factors in Computing Systems. – 2020. – P. 1–10.

11. Shinohara K. Barriers to the Use of Assistive Technology for Visually Impaired People // International Journal of Disability Management. – 2022. – Vol. 5.

12. Patel N., Sharma P., Brown B., Peterson T. Haptic Feedback Systems for Navigation of Visually Impaired People: A Review // IEEE Transactions on Haptics. – 2021. – Vol. 14, No. 4. – P. 783–798.

13. Антонюк В. М., Повшенко О. А. Пристрій просторової орієнтації з гаптичним зворотним зв'язком для людей з порушенням зору // Ефективність та автоматизація інженерних рішень у приладобудуванні: збірник праць XXI Всеукраїнської науково-практичної конференції студентів, аспірантів та молодих вчених, 10–11 грудня 2025 р. – 2025. – С. 144–146.

14. Zhang D., Smith S., Peterson J. Time-of-Flight (ToF) Sensing Principle and Its Applications in High-Precision Robotics and Navigation // Journal of Positioning Systems. – 2020. – DOI: 10.1109/JPS.2020.3005876.

15. Tsuji S., Kohama T. Omnidirectional Proximity Sensor System for Drones Using Optical Time-of-Flight Sensors // IEEE Transactions on Electrical and Electronic Engineering. – 2022. – Vol. 17. – P. 19–25. – DOI: 10.1002/tee.23483.

16. Rantala J. Spatial Touch in Presenting Information with Mobile Devices // Thesis. – 2014. – Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269399688_Spatial_Touch_in_Presenting_Information_with_Mobile_Devices

17. STMicroelectronics. VL53L7CX Time-of-Flight Multizone Distance Sensor Datasheet. – Available: <https://www.alldatasheet.com/datasheet-pdf/view/1447576/STMICROELECTRONICS/VL53L7CX.html>

18. NanJing Top Power ASIC Corp. TP4056 Complete Constant-Current/Constant-Voltage Linear Charger for Single Cell Lithium-Ion Batteries Datasheet. – Available: <https://www.alldatasheet.com/datasheet-pdf/view/1132405/ASIC/TP4056.html>